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Blade strain measurements of cross-flow turbines with varying blade materials and unsupported blade span

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Abstract

The objective of this work was to investigate cross-flow turbine (CFT) performance in relation to varying blade characteristics by using blade strain measurements correlated with overall turbine torque and thrust data. This involved conducting experiments with a 1-meter diameter vertical-axis CFT consisting of three NACA 0018 blades with two support struts in a turbine test bed in the University of New Hampshire (UNH) towing tank. The impact of blade deformation on turbine performance was examined by varying both the blade materials and support strut position. A novel technique of measuring blade strain on CFTs was employed by embedding high-resolution low-noise distributed fiber optic sensors. Turbine performance was measured by varying tow speed and tip speed ratios. Each power curve utilized a towing speed that was sufficiently high for the performance to be independent of Reynolds number. Strain measurements were correlated to overall turbine torque and thrust. The experimental results provide insight into the impact of blade deformation on turbine performance. The collected dataset is currently being used to validate fluid-structure interaction models.

Keywords: tidal turbine; blade strain; fiber optics; tow tank experiments

1. Introduction

There is an urgent need to reduce carbon emissions and diversify the global energy supply. The oceans are a largely untapped resource regarding their tidal, wave, and ocean current energy potential and could significantly contribute to clean energy objectives with a technical resource of about 1,670 TWh/yr [1]. Cross-flow turbines (CFTs) can be used to extract energy from tidal, river or ocean currents and provide electric energy to the grid. However, one of their main barriers to market entry is their levelized cost of energy (LCOE), which at present is still quite high. CFTs can become a more cost-competitive technology by using less rigid, less expensive materials and by reducing the number of necessary blade supports.

Previous studies have shown how CFT performance was affected by blade geometry mainly for wind [2- 6] and some for water [7 – 13], by blade-wake interactions [14 – 17], by operating conditions [18 – 21], and by how cross-flow turbine blades are affixed to the shaft of the turbine [22]. To our knowledge, there are no studies that have investigated the combination of varying blade material and unsupported blade span. These parameters are potentially

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key to lowering the LCOE, by using less rigid, less expensive materials, and reducing the number of struts required to support the blades. However, the selection of blade materials and unsupported blade span can modify turbine dynamics if large deflections occur. Tidal turbines, particularly CFTs, are inherently unsteady devices and their components are susceptible to fatigue. Understanding component reliability and survivability is critical to the progress of the technology in terms of performance and cost [23 - 25].

Strain measurements are commonly used to determine the deformation of members that undergo external forcing. Many researchers have used single-point strain sensors to measure blade strain on tidal turbine rotors such as in [23, 24, 26-29] which typically use either scattering techniques with optical time-domain reflectometry or fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) that are limited by the number of gratings that can be multiplexed in a single fiber [30]. Sensors that use these techniques do not provide high resolution data along the blade span to determine the full blade behavior during operation. This research presents a novel method of measuring blade strain in cross-flow turbine blades by embedding a high-definition distributed fiber optic strain sensor. The primary goal of this research was to evaluate turbine performance using low-cost components.

Nomenclature

A	turbine swept area [m ²]
D	turbine diameter [m]
c	blade chord length [m]
c_p	power coefficient
N	number of blades
r	turbine radius [m]
Re_D	turbine diameter-based Reynolds number
T	turbine thrust force [N]
U_∞	free-stream velocity [m/s]
λ	tip speed ratio
ν	water kinematic viscosity [m ² /s]
ω	shaft angular velocity [rad/s]
ρ	water density [kg/m ³]
σ	turbine solidity

2. Methods

2.1. Facility

Experimental tests were performed in the large cross-section towing tank at the University of New Hampshire Chase Ocean Engineering laboratory. The tank is a 36m-long, 3.66m-wide, and 2.44m-deep facility with a carriage system that can tow objects in static water. An electronics cabinet with AC power outlets, motor drive interfaces, and a data acquisition (DAQ) system with National Instrument modules are on the carriage and serve to communicate with sensors and sample simultaneously. The facility includes an instrumented marine hydrokinetic turbine test bed (TTB) frame of NACA 0020 foils with 0.140 m chord that can be mounted on the tow carriage, with CFTs installed within the frame in a vertical axis configuration. The overall TTB drag and added resistive torque from the bearings were accounted for in turbine measurements.

2.2. Turbine model

The impact of blade deformation on turbine performance was examined by varying the blade materials and support strut position. A modular 1-meter diameter CFT with three NACA 0018 straight blades with 0.9 m span and two horizontal support struts was developed to test the varying structural properties (Fig. 1). The lower strut was fixed at one end of the blades, while the upper strut was adjusted to five positions changing the length of the free end: $z/H = 1.0, 0.75, 0.5, 0.25,$ and 0.14 , where z is the distance between the upper and lower struts and H is the overall blade span. The blades have a chord length of 0.095 m and were mounted to the struts at mid-chord. The turbine solidity,

$\sigma = Nc/\pi D$, is 0.09 and with a chord-to-radius ratio, c/r , of 0.19. Due to the chord-to-radius ratio, the rotor is considered to have high solidity.

Fig. 1. The high deflection hydrofoil rotor in a cross-section view of the UNH tow tank and turbine test bed frame.

When selecting the materials for CFT blades, it was important to consider their durability for this application. Composite materials are popular in marine energy due to their non-corrosive properties and high specific strength and stiffness [31]. Additionally, [31] suggests that fibers can be aligned with the main loads to increase their strength. Carbon is one of the most common fiber reinforcement materials used in tidal turbine blades [32] and is known to be rigid but expensive, at approximately US\$17 – US\$45 per kg [33]. Glass composites may be used in marine applications and are less expensive at approximately US\$1 - US\$2 per kg [33] but have a lower modulus of elasticity compared to carbon fiber composites. [34] tested e-glass fiber coupons by immersion for 2.5 years with accelerated aging to represent 18 years, showing that the coupons absorb relatively small amounts of water. However, there was about a 20% reduction of fatigue strength in the immersion aged coupons compared to unaged dry coupons. Among other materials, [32] tested specimens of carbon fiber composites and less expensive glass composites for their aged reduction of strength after water saturation. The carbon fiber specimen retained its strength properties well, while the strength of the glass composite specimen was affected similarly to the tests conducted by [34]. [34] asserts that the effect of water saturation is a limited degradation in fatigue strength, mostly at high cycle life, and that glass composites are a viable tidal turbine blade material option.

The carbon fiber composite blades serve as a reference and were constructed of Gurit Carbon Fiber SparPreg. SparPreg is a unidirectional prepreg specifically designed for the lay-up of thick sections, such as that for wind turbine blades. A total of 32 plies each with a thickness of 0.586 mm were laid in a closed mold and oven-cured to create a symmetric solid. Composites are inherently anisotropic, and the fibers were advantageously laid for higher stiffness in the spanwise direction. From [35], a conservative maximum allowable strain for carbon fiber composites is 0.24%. The E-glass fiber composite blades were constructed from Gurit Glass Fiber SparPreg. Similar to the carbon fiber blades, a total of 32 plies each of 0.586 mm in thickness were laid in a closed mold and oven-cured. The laminate was symmetric and anisotropic. From [35], a conservative maximum allowable strain for E-glass fiber composites is 0.35%. The hollow e-glass fiber composite blades were made of a skin of Gurit glass composite and seven plies of glass fabric. The glass was vacuum infused with an epoxy resin, as epoxy-based laminates have excellent fatigue resistance when compared to polyester and vinylester [33]. The internal void was filled with Shore D urethane casting resin to create a flexible center. From [35], a conservative maximum allowable strain for carbon fiber composites is 0.35%.

2.3. Blade strain measurements

To capture blade deflection, high-resolution and high-frequency strain measurements were used to assess blade loading during turbine operation. Fiber optic sensors are a safe sensing option as they do not require power at the sensor, are immune to electromagnetic interference (EMI), and are compatible with embedment in composites [30].

This research presents a novel method of measuring blade strain in CFT blades by using Luna Innovation's high-definition distributed fiber optic strain sensors that employ swept-wavelength interferometry (SWI) to measure Rayleigh backscatter, resulting in high-resolution measurements along the length of the fiber. The sensors were embedded on both sides of two out of the three blades for each material type. The fiber optic sensor was used with Luna Innovation's single channel optical distributed sensor interrogator (ODiSI) 6100, remote module, dedicated instrument controller, and a 50 m standoff cable.

2.4. Test plan and data analysis

To minimize Reynolds number (Re) scaling effects, the carriage can tow the setup at sufficiently high speeds to reach Re independence. It was an iterative process between Re dependence and performance tests. For Re dependence tests, the tip speed ratio λ for which peak torque was expected to occur was held constant while varying Re by tow speed. This allowed for identification of a tow speed when the power coefficient became independent of change in Re . In the second series of experimental tests, the tow speed remained constant at what is determined to be Re independent and λ was varied. When the peak power coefficient occurred at a different λ than what was used during the Re dependence tests, the Re dependence tests were repeated. Each of the experimental tests were repeated three times before adjusting the strut position to increase the number of data points for analysis of each configuration. The tip speed ratio is defined as the ratio between tangential blade velocity and the free-stream velocity:

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega (D/2)}{U_\infty}. \quad (1)$$

The turbine diameter Reynolds number describes a ratio between inertial to viscous forces:

$$Re_D = \frac{U_\infty D}{\nu}. \quad (2)$$

The power coefficient is the ratio of rotor power to the fluid power:

$$C_p = \frac{T\omega}{\frac{1}{2}\rho A U_\infty^3}. \quad (3)$$

3. Results

The Re independence tests were first conducted by maintaining a tip speed ratio of 2.5, which is the expected tip speed ratio at peak power for this rotor. The turbine diameter-based Re was adjusted by increasing the tow speed of the carriage. A tow speed of 1.1 m/s was determined to be sufficiently high to remove Re effects (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of Reynolds number on turbine performance with $\lambda = 2.5$ and varying free end length. CF, EG, and HEG represent carbon fiber, E-glass fiber, and hollow E-glass fiber respectively.

The performance of the turbine is shown in Fig. 3, with C_p averaged over each turbine revolution across three trials. Each blade material type is represented by differing symbols and the color gradient represents the strut position, with the darkest being the struts farthest away from one-another and the lightest being the struts closest to one-another. The tow speed was maintained at 1.1 m/s while the tip speed ratio was varied. However, the maximum allowable strain

was reached for the configuration with hollow e-glass blades at z/H of 0.25. Therefore, tests for that case were run at a tow speed of 1.0 m/s. The results revealed a near equivalent peak C_P for the carbon fiber and E-glass fiber blades at z/H of 0.50 and 0.75. The configuration with hollow e-glass blades overall did not perform as well as the rotor with carbon fiber or E-glass blades. However, there was a slight increase in performance at the most rigid strut separation distances, z/H of 0.50 and 0.75.

Fig. 3. Turbine performance with $U_\infty = 1.1$ m/s a) at a range of λ with varying free end length, and b) at a maximum C_P with varying free end length. CF, EG, and HEG represent carbon fiber, E-glass fiber, and hollow E-glass fiber respectively.

For each blade material type, the maximum microstrain for each strut configuration was investigated. The carbon fiber blades experienced the least amount of strain, while the microstrain measurements were similar for both E-glass and hollow E-glass blades. Strain measurements are not presented here due to page limits, but will be presented and discussed at the UMERC conference.

4. Conclusions

The results indicate that it is feasible to use less expensive, less rigid materials without sacrificing performance. The rotor with E-glass blades performed almost identically to the rotor with the reference carbon fiber blades at the most rigid strut configurations. To minimize the number of struts required, a strut separation distance of at least $z/H = 0.75$ should be used with E-glass blades. An analysis that looks at the cost trade-off between the number of struts and the blade material type would be dependent on the rotor design. The number of struts can be minimized only to an extent without sacrificing performance. As evidenced by the hollow E-glass blades, there are limitations that highly deflective blade materials will result in poor performance and there are only small differences between strain measurements of the E-glass and hollow E-glass blades. The collected dataset is currently being used to verify and validate fluid-structure interaction models to understand the reliability and survivability of CFTs with these blade materials and strut configurations. Additionally, a cost analysis that includes the fatigue strength degradation of E-glass composites at high cycle life will be conducted.

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